

HERPES SIMPLEX ENCEPHALITIS AS A FATAL DISEASE

التهاب الدماغ بفيروس الحلاّ البسيط كمرض قاتل

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ملخص الحالة

يعتبر التهاب الدماغ بفيروس الحلاّ البسيط حالة إنتانية قاتلة تترافق مع وقيّات مرتفعة عند عدم معالجتها أو إغفال تشخيصها. يمكن أن يتظاهر هذا الالتهاب بأعراض حادة كالصداع، الحمى، الاختلاجات والتخليط الذهني. في بعض الحالات يساء تشخيص هذه الحالة بداية بكونها التهاب سحايا قبل إجراء التصوير بالرنين المغناطيسي، وبذلك يفقد المريض فرصته بالبقاء بسبب تأخر التشخيص، وتأخر البدء بالعلاج بالنتيجة. إن الرّبط بين القصة السريرية، الفحص الفيزيائي، موجودات التصوير المقطعي المحوسب للدماغ CT، التصوير بالرنين المغناطيسي MRI وتحليل السائل الدماغي الشوكي يستخدم لإثبات التشخيص. نقوم هنا بعرض حالة نادرة من التهاب الدماغ بفيروس الحلاّ البسيط نظّاهرت بقصة تخليط ذهني، حمى، عدم توجّه مع نتائج غير نوعية لفحص السائل الدماغي الشوكي، تطوّرت الحالة لاحقاً لحدوث اختلاجات. تماشت موجودات التصوير بالرنين المغناطيسي مع التهاب دماغ، كما أظهر تفاعل سلسلة البوليميراز PCR الذي تم إجراؤه على عينة من السائل الدماغي الشوكي إيجابية للحمض النووي لفيروس الحلاّ البسيط النمط الأول. لسوء الحظ، كانت مراجعة المريض للمشفى متأخرة ورغم المعالجة بالأسيكلوفير فقد توفّي خلال أسبوعين. يجب أخذ تشخيص التهاب الدماغ بفيروس الحلاّ البسيط بعين الاعتبار عند كل مريض غير متوجّه مع وجود سبات أو اختلاجات. يمكن للتصوير بالرنين المغناطيسي أن يعطي الصورة الأمثل لتوجيه المعالجة في مثل هذه الحالات.

ABSTRACT

Herpes simplex encephalitis (HSE) is a fatal infectious disease with high mortality if misdiagnosed or untreated. It can presents with acute features such as a headache, fever, seizures and confusion. It sometimes suspected as meningitis before MRI, and then the patient loses a chance for survival because of late diagnosis, and late treatment as a result. The combination of clinical history and examination, brain computed tomography scan, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) analysis have been used to establish the diagnosis. Here, we are presenting a rare case of HSE presenting as confusion, fever and disorientation with nonspecific CSF analysis, then seizures, and typical MRI findings consistent with HSE and CSF polymerase chain reaction positive for herpes simplex

virus-1 DNA. Unfortunately the diagnosis was late, and even with acyclovir the patient died after 2 weeks. Herpes simplex encephalitis must be suspected in a patient with disoriented with coma or seizures, and MRI gives the best view for direction the management.

INTRODUCTION

Infection with HSE can cause acute viral encephalitis and various neurological disorders, including meningo-encephalitis. It can be fatal if not treated. It can associate with high mortality.¹ It is the cause of acute viral encephalitis in 50-70% of cases where a virus can be identified.²

Both HSV-1 vs HSV-2 can cause encephalitis (HSE),

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but studies refers to HSV-1 as a major reason for more than 80% of cases in all adults.³ It correlated with high morbidity, even with treatment, and after treatment. survivor patients will suffer from neural disorders later, and most of them died through the first year after infection.⁴ Diagnostic delay is associated with poorer prognosis, because it affects the beginning of treatment, thus leading to deterioration in the patient's overall status.⁵ Acyclovir is the drug of choice for treatment that decreases mortality and morbidity in acute HSV encephalitis.⁶ The outcome depends on the period from the beginning of symptoms, and starting acyclovir treatment.⁷

CASE PRESENTATION

A case report of a 46-years-old male who presented to the hospital by his relatives with a history of fever $\geq 39^\circ$, exacerbations of disoriented and headache with vomiting the last 7 days. He was suspected as an infection and they presented him to the hospital when he started lethargy two days ago. There was a history of low-grade fever at beginning which advanced. No night sweats or weight loss, and no last inflammations in neck. He has influenza the last two weeks. The patient complains at the beginning only from some feeling of fatigue and fever with headache.

Physical examination revealed a sick man, partial coma. He was disoriented with low mobility response. He did not have neck stiffness or other meningeal signs. The chest X-ray was normal. Glasgow score was 12. He advanced seizures in the hospital before he goes in a coma. Investigations carried out included complete blood count, hemoglobin 13.6 g/dl, white blood cell $14.01 \times 10^3/\text{ul}$. The C-reactive protein (CRP) was normal. A CT-scan was performed on admission, and before lumbar puncture, there's no edema or hemorrhage. A lumbar puncture was also performed. The CSF results were as follows: $7 \text{ cells}/\text{mm}^3$ with lymphocyte predominance (95%), Glucose 62 mg/dl, and Total protein 76 mg/dl.

MRI scan was performed which showed hyperintense depiction on the temporal lobes on 2 sides in

FLAIR sequence, as in Figure 1, T2WI as in Figure 2. A CSF sample was sent to PCR, and was positive for HSV type I (6693 copies/ml). Therapeutic regimen of the patient included acyclovir 15 mg/kg/8 h, levetiracetam 500 mg/12 h, and dexamethasone. Unfortunately; the patient was late, and the delay of treatment gives so poor prognosis, he died after 17 days with heart arrest.

DISCUSSION

Clinical manifestations, signs and symptoms, imaging studies (including CT brain and MRI), and CSF (analysis and cultures) are the keys of right diagnostic in encephalitis.

Fever, consciousness disorders, disorientation, as in our case, behavioral disorders, language disorders, seizures and focal neurologic deficit constitute the typical signs and symptoms of HSV encephalitis.^{8,9} Urgently performing a brain CT scan should be considered in suspected cases of HSV encephalitis, prior to lumbar puncture, when one or more of the following are present: evidence of obstructive raised intracranial pressure, Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) <13 , fall in GCS >2 , focal neurological signs, abnormal posturing, papillo-edema, and immune-compromise.¹⁰ According to the diagnostic criteria for encephalitis¹¹ that explained in Table 1, and to the laboratory and imaging study, the diagnosis of encephalitis suspected.

Our patient established the major criteria and 4 minor criterion. HSV CSF PCR test is the gold standard method for the diagnosis of HSV encephalitis.¹² Most usual radiologic features in HSV encephalitis are as follows: (1) hypodense lesions of temporal lobes and orbitofrontal regions, sometimes with petechial hemorrhage on brain CT scanning (2) hypointensity in T1 and hyperintensity in T2 images on brain MRI scanning.¹³

According to the study conducted by Chow et al. in patients with manifestations of encephalitis and temporal lobe abnormalities on MRI scan, the presence of bilateral temporal lobe involvement and lesions outside the temporal lobe, insula, or cingulate

Major criteria (required):	Minor criteria (2 required for possible encephalitis; ≥ 3 required for probable or confirmed ^a encephalitis):
<p>Patients presenting to medical attention with altered mental status (defined as decreased or altered level of consciousness, lethargy or personality change) lasting ≥ 24 h with no alternative cause identified.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Documented fever $\geq 38^{\circ}\text{C}$ (100.4°F) within the 72 h before or after presentation. 2. Generalized or partial seizures not fully attributable to a preexisting seizure disorder. 3. New onset of focal neurologic findings. 4. CSF WBC count $\geq 5/\text{mm}^3$. 5. Abnormality of brain parenchyma on neuroimaging suggestive of encephalitis that is either new from prior studies or appears acute in onset. 6. Abnormality on electroencephalography that is consistent with encephalitis and not attributable to another cause.

Table 1. Diagnostic criteria for encephalitis and encephalopathy.

Figure 1. MRI scan was performed which showed hyper-intense depiction on the temporal lobes on 2 sides in FLAIR sequence.

Figure 2. MRI scan was performed which showed hyper-intense depiction on the temporal lobes on 2 sides in T2W sequence.

were less frequently seen in patients with HSV encephalitis.¹⁴ Temporal lobe is included bilateral in our patient. It is possible that joint use of antiviral and corticosteroid medications may become the standard for the treatment of HSV encephalitis.¹⁵ Our patient was treated with acyclovir set of the symptoms according to Erdem et al.¹⁶ Our patient was male and he was in a state of delay for initiation of acyclovir, and at last, he died.

CONCLUSIONS

Herpes simplex encephalitis is a fatal infection needs a high induced from the physician. It must be suspected in every patient presents with altered mental status (defined as decreased or altered level of consciousness, lethargy or personality change) lasting ≥ 24 h with no alternative cause identified, with fever $\geq 38^{\circ}\text{C}$ and seizures or other neural disorders. The initiation of acyclovir can saves

the life time, so with a patient established the criteria of encephalitis, start acyclovir, even before the result of PCR.

REFERENCES

1. Baten A, Desai M, Melo-Bicchi M, et al. Continuous electroencephalogram as a biomarker of disease progression and severity in Herpes Simplex Virus-1 encephalitis. *Clin EEG Neuro* 2019 Mar 15;1550059419835705.
2. Tyler KL. Acute viral encephalitis. *New Eng J Med* 2018 Aug;379(6):557-66.
3. Aggarwal P, Wali JP, Singh S, et al. A clinico-bacteriological study of peripheral tuberculous lymphadenitis. *J Ass Phys India* 2001 Aug;49:808-12.
4. Raschilas F, Wolff M, Delatour F, et al. Outcome of and prognostic factors for herpes simplex encephalitis in adult patients: results of a multicenter study. *Clin Infect Dis* 2002 Aug;35(3):254-60.
5. Bae MH, Lee NR, Han YM, et al. Bilateral acute retinal necrosis and encephalo-malacia due to Herpes Simplex Virus infection in a premature infant. *Neonatal Med* 2019 Feb;26(1):63-6.
6. Amalakanti S, Boppana SH. Antiviral therapy for Herpes Simplex Virus encephalitis: Systematic review and meta analysis of RCTs. Available at SSRN 3347915. 2019 Mar 3.
7. Fallah P, Heidari AE, Kalantar E, et al. Herpes simplex encephalitis: successful treatment with Acyclovir. *J Paramed Scien* 2019 Jan;10(1):19886.
8. Fillatre P, Crabol Y, Morand P, et al. Infectious encephalitis: Management without etiological diagnosis 48 hours after onset. *Médec Maladies Infect* 2017 May;47(3):236-51.
9. Petit Pedrol M. Antigenes and mechanisms of immune-mediated encephalitis (Doctoral dissertation, Universitat de Barcelona).
10. Solomon T, Michael BD, Smith PE, Management of suspected viral encephalitis in adults-association of British Neurologists and British Infection Association National Guidelines. *J Infect* 2012 Apr;64(4):347-73.
11. Dubey D, Pittock SJ, Kelly CR, et al. Autoimmune encephalitis epidemiology and a comparison to infectious encephalitis. *Ann Neurol* 2018 Jan;83(1):166-77.
12. Whitley RJ. Herpes simplex encephalitis: adolescents and adults. *Antiviral Res* 2006 Sep;71(2-3):141-8.
13. Sener RN. Diffusion MRI in Rasmussen's encephalitis, herpes simplex encephalitis, and bacterial meningoencephalitis. *Computer Med Imag Graph* 2002 Sep;26(5):327-32.
14. Chou CH, Yang TL, Wang CP. Ultrasonographic features of tuberculous cervical lymphadenitis. *J Med Ultrasound* 2014 Sep;22(3):158-63.
15. Gilbert GJ. Herpes Simplex encephalitis triggering anti-NMDAR encephalitis. *Neurology* 2014 Jun;82(22):2041.
16. Erdem H, Cag Y, Ozturk-Engin D, et al. Results of a multinational study suggest the need for rapid diagnosis and early antiviral treatment at the onset of herpetic meningoencephalitis. *Antimicrob Agent Chemother* 2015 Jun;59(6):3084-9.